

EVALUATING A HIGH DYNAMIC RANGE ALGORITHM FOR REAL-TIME MICROSCOPIC INSPECTION SYSTEMS.

Salvador García Bernal ^(1,2), Chi Zheng ^(1,2), Keqi Zhang ⁽¹⁾,
Lei Mao ⁽¹⁾, Cuifang Kuang ⁽²⁾, Xu Liu ⁽²⁾

(1) Ningbo Yongxin Optics CO., LTD.

No.385 Mingzhou Road, Hi-Tech Industry Park

315040, Ningbo, China

e-mail: sgb@yxopt.com, zc@yxopt.com, zkq@yxopt.com, ml@yxopt.com

(2) State Key Laboratory of Modern Optical Instrumentations

Zhejiang University

Hangzhou, China

e-mail: Cfkuang@zju.edu.cn, liuxu@zju.edu.cn

Abstract. High Dynamic Range (HDR) Imaging/Video is an important part of the microscopic analysis. In this paper, common methods for obtaining a well-exposed image/video are briefly reviewed, then an alternative method to generate high-quality HDR video in real-time is proposed and compared using general objective metrics for its correct interpretation. The primary application of this implementation is for real-time of non-high speed microscopic inspection systems. Several highly reflective samples are evaluated and compared between this state-of-the-art algorithm and other common methods. Results have shown the success of the described method. This publication can serve as a baseline for further evaluation and inspection in the field of HDR Microscopy.

Keywords: Image sensors, high dynamic range video, image fusion, inspection microscopy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Daily life scenes have a wide dynamic range luminance content. Using the well-known multi-exposure techniques have been shown to effectively capture most of these lumina range. Majority of digital images and devices use eight bits per channel, given as a result of the compressed representation of the real range into a 256 discrete level. Quantizing the actual wide range into discrete levels allows us to recover the actual luminance content only partially. This low dynamic range set is used to combine the best parts of each individual pixel. The most challenging part is to obtain the sequential exposure set because it depends on sensor's speed. The second challenge is the proper combination of these pixels and generation of the final high dynamic range frame, ideally, in real-time. In this paper, an effective method to combine these pixels in real-time is introduced. This algorithm can be used with multiple-exposures [1],[2], multi-sensors [3],[4],[5] and single sensor with spatially varying exposures [6],[7]. One advantage of multi-exposure is the use of any standard sensor without resolution loss, but some artefacts, such as ghosting are introduced in the final rendering. Multi-sensor allows us to use up to four sensors at the same time with the same resolution, the only disadvantage is the effective use of the light with special optics. Spatially varying exposures reduce the spatial resolution of the final rendering due to the microarray used over the pixels. On the other hand, less or not-at-all artefacts caused by movement are shown in the final rendering. For proof of concept, we showed the real-time implementation using the multiple-exposures technique. This will be a feasible solution for the majority of standard image sensors.

2 METHODS FOR HDR ESTIMATION

There are many well-known methods to obtain High Dynamic Range (HDR) images. But, many of them are not straightforward to apply for live video. In this section, we consider the most important methods for rendering from multiple-exposures to a high dynamic range single output. This will be used as a reference and as comparative for the results of the processed approach described in this paper.

2.1 Generating HDR Maps

The main common point in all HDR methods is the correct capturing of a set of usable exposures. For that reason, it is necessary to have an image sensor that is able to control different exposure settings. In one previous work, it was seen that separation time among exposures should be estimated to obtain a stable bracketing. After that, an alignment and/or optical flow algorithm is applied to avoid misalignment and ghosting. Many researchers came up with some interesting solutions [8], [9]. The only disadvantage is that most of these methods cannot be effectively used in real-time systems. Once that the pre-processed set of frames are obtained the

proper merging is applied. Once the HDR map is obtained the data is compressed based on a Tone Mapping procedure.

2.2 Debevec and Malik exposure Merging

This algorithm [10] is based on the concept that a particular pixel exposure is defined as a product of the irradiance at the film and the exposure time, transferred by the camera response function. Knowing this, the objective function is minimised to determine the camera response curve. This process of recovering the response curve requires to solve a set of linear equations based on SVD (Single Value Decomposition) method. In more detail, it is made the assumption its response curve is monotonic and invertible:

$$\ln f^{-1}(Z_{ij}) = \ln E_i + \ln \Delta t_j \quad (1)$$

Here E_i is the irradiance for each pixel and Δt_j the exposure time, Z_{ij} the current pixel. A weighted function defined by the hat function to smooth the terms of the recovered curve is defined by:

$$w(z) = \begin{cases} z - Z_{min} & z \leq \frac{1}{2}(Z_{min} + Z_{max}) \\ Z_{max} - z & z > \frac{1}{2}(Z_{min} + Z_{max}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Using this weighted function in the objective function, it can be used for the camera response curve as follows:

$$O = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^P w(Z_{ij}) [g(Z_{ij}) - \ln E_i - \ln \Delta t_j]^2 + \lambda \sum_{z=Z_{min}+1}^{Z_{max}-1} w(z) g''(z) r^2 \quad (3)$$

In this manner the main function for recovering the response curve $g()$ allows estimating the new radiance pixels. Finally, for making the final rendering from the set of exposures, it is used the weighted average function defined by:

$$\ln E_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^P w(Z_{ij})(g(Z_{ij}) - \ln \Delta t_j)}{\sum_{j=1}^P w(Z_{ij})} \quad (4)$$

2.3 Mertens Merging

This technique [11] blends multiple-exposures, based on simple quality measures like contrast, saturation and well-exposedness. Each pixel used this information to obtain weighted combination given by:

$$W_{ij,k} = C_{ij,k}^{\omega_C} x_{ij,k}^{\omega_S} x_{ij,k}^{\omega_E} \quad (5)$$

here C, S and E represent contrast, saturation and well-exposedness, $\omega_C, \omega_S, \omega_E$ are the weighting exponents. (i, j) refers to the current pixel in the k -th image. Then a weighted average is used over the quality measure to obtain a consistent result. The resulting image it is blended by:

$$L\{R\}_{ij}^l = \sum_{k=1}^N G\{\hat{W}\}_{ij,k}^l L\{I\}_{ij,k} \quad (6)$$

with \hat{W} being the Gaussian weighted average, $I_{ij,k}$ the current pixel of the current absolute Laplacian image of the sequence. Finally, $L\{R\}$ is collapsed to obtain R , the resulting blending image.

2.4 Ahmet Merging Function

A set of images with different exposure are used to render a HDR frame. The final rendering contains details in both dark and light areas. This merging function [12] is defined as:

$$O_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g(p_{ij})w(p_{ij})}{\Delta t_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^N w(p_{ij})} \quad (7)$$

N is the number of images, p is the value of pixel j in image i , $g()$ is the camera response function, w the weighted contribution (see Eq.2) and Δ_t the exposure time in image i .

2.5 Global Average

A very simple method for combining a set of multiple-exposures that is used as the reference, it is the global average or general pixel average. This function is defined as:

$$R = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{I_{ij,k}}{N} \quad (8)$$

All pixels in this function will have the same weighted value, the final render will be used as the reference for comparing the visual appearance on the quality metrics for evaluating these algorithms.

2.6 A General Tone Mapping

For visualising the HDR map, a process of scaling or mapping is required. The tone mapping will allow us to represent the HDR information into an LDR map

easily manageable for any standard output device (Image Display). For practical implementation, a general tone mapping is used. The Reinhard operator [16] first use a scaling that is analogous to setting exposure in a camera. Then, it is to apply automatic dodging-and-burning to accomplish dynamic range compression if need it. The initial mapping function is defined by:

$$L_d(x, y) = \frac{L(x, y) \left(1 + \frac{L(x, y)}{L_{white}^2}\right)}{1 + L(x, y)} \quad (9)$$

where L_{white} can be the maximum luminance in the scene to avoid burn-out. $L(x, y)$ is the scaled luminance computed by:

$$L(x, y) = \frac{a}{\hat{L}_w} L_w(x, y) \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{L}_w = \frac{1}{N} \exp\left(\sum_{x, y} \log(\delta + L_w(x, y))\right)$$

here $L_w(x, y)$ is the current luminance of the HDR map, N total number of pixels in the HDR map, δ a small value to avoid singularity when the \exp it is applied. a a constant value (key value) that normally moves from 0.009 to 0.40. If the dodging-and-burning applied a threshold value is computed as:

$$|V(x, y, s_m)| < \epsilon \quad (11)$$

here V is given by:

$$V(x, y, s) = \frac{V_1(x, y, s) - V_2(x, y, s)}{2^\phi a / s^2 + V_1(x, y, s)} \quad (12)$$

ϕ, a are the key value and a sharpening parameter respectively. V_1, V_2 are given by the convolution of the current luminance HDR map and the Gaussian function defined by:

$$R_i(x, y, s) = \frac{1}{\pi(\alpha_i s)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{(\alpha_i s)^2}\right) \quad (13)$$

3 METRICS FOR HDR EVALUATION

For evaluating our algorithm an objective image/frame quality metric is used. This mathematical model will give us a numeric comparison based on the reference images. This will be explained in a further section.

3.1 Signal-to-Noise Ratio

For each set of images, it is calculated its average HDR/TMO value and the standard deviation. The first parameter will give us information about the signal level and the second the level of noise. In this manner we can:

$$SNR = 20 \text{Log}_{10} \left(\frac{\bar{E}_i}{\sigma_i} \right) \quad (14)$$

3.2 Minkowski Metric [13]

The similarity between the reference and distorted or recovered image is calculated as:

$$E_\gamma = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [|x_i - y_i|]^\gamma \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \quad (15)$$

x_i, y_i are the reference and recovered image respectively, N the number of samples over the image. Gamma factor among: $\gamma \in (1, \infty)$.

3.3 Sharpness Metric

The estimation of this metric considers how sharp the resulting or current image is. According to Windisch [14], the variance is less prone to noise. Also, on less sharp images its variance will decrease. The function for sharpness metric based on the variance is:

$$f_v = \frac{1}{NM} \sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} [g(i, j) - \bar{g}]^2 \quad (16)$$

where $\bar{g}, g(i, j)$ are the average intensity and the current pixel on the image, respectively.

3.4 HDR-VQM

An objective quality measure based on the High Dynamic Range - Video Quality Measure (HDR-VQM) [15] is used to evaluate the quality of the renderings. This metric is adapted for our case. First, as is mentioned by Narwaria, a typical visual field based on the quantity W is computed as:

$$W = \tan(2^\circ) V \sqrt{\frac{R}{D_A}} \quad (17)$$

where V is the viewing distance in cm, R is the display resolution and D_A is the display area. For our case, we consider V base distance of 100cm and R full HD

resolution with $D \approx 1258cm^2$. Based on this factor, its calculated the ST region. The original HDR-VQM equation is designed for video systems, and as is mentioned in the paper that is possible to compute HDR image quality as well.

$$HDR - VQM = \frac{ST_v}{|v \in L_p|} \quad (18)$$

where L_p denotes the set with lowest $p\%$ values, for our experiments this is rated at 5%. Ideally, a perfect video will have a zero $HDR - VQM$ value, thus a lower value will tell us that the image has higher quality.

4 FAST MERGING EXTENDED RANGE

The following algorithm is the basis for a more general one, it is called Fast Merging Extended Range (FMER) where $n \geq 2$ input frames are required. These frames are typically low dynamic range frames differently exposed and can be acquired using multiple-exposures and/or multi-sensor systems. It is feasible to implement it in hardware for spatially varying sensors due to its simplicity and quality.

4.1 Algorithm Formulation

Let's consider a set of two consecutive or parallel normalised frames.

Each frame its analysed the local luminance kernel weights $w(n)$ of a 3x3 convolutional window, i represents the current pixel and is computed as:

$$w(n) = \frac{1}{9} \sum_{i=0}^9 L(i) \quad (19)$$

where L is calculated using $REC.2020$ coefficients L'_{RGB} where RGB are the original triplet of the frame, as follows:

$$L = \left(\sum L'_{RGB} \right)^{(1/2.2)} \quad (20)$$

$$L'_{RGB} = \begin{bmatrix} R * 0.2627^{2.2} \\ G * 0.6780^{2.2} \\ B * 0.0593^{2.2} \end{bmatrix}$$

A weighted arithmetic combination is used to find the weighted central pixel for $i - 1$, as we are considering two frames: $w(1), w(2)$ this is:

$$s = \frac{8 * w(1) + 8 * w(2)}{18} \quad (21)$$

We define a logarithmic function that is used as a control factor for the pixels to use. This is generated as lookup function and it is used to find the mapped value of the weighted combination. For calculating this curve it is taken a set of images that cover the full exposure range. In our case, 25 images were enough. After that

it is analysed a central region and calculate its equivalent luminance, this data is plotted and approximated to a logarithmic function, therefore:

$$f_s(s) = \log(7.5(s + 0.006)^2 + 0.98) \quad (22)$$

The central pixel of $w(n)$ can fall in one of these conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} if w_{(1,1)}(1) \geq w_{(1,1)}(2) & \quad p_a = f(1)_{1,1}, p_b = f(2)_{1,1} \\ otherwise & \quad p_a = f(2)_{1,1}, p_b = f(1)_{1,1} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $f(n)_{(1,1)}$, it is the original central pixel from the n^{th} frame. Finally, the merging $O(x, y)_{RGB}$ considers the result of the lookup function.

$$O(x, y)_{RGB} = p_a * (1 - f_s(s)) + p_b * f_s(s) \quad (24)$$

4.2 Adjusting Mapping Controls (Details, Contrast and Saturation)

The $O(x, y)_{RGB}$ values contain floating point values that are adjusted with a mapping control. The function takes $O(x, y)_{RGB}$ to produce a new $O'(x, y)_{RGB}$, this operator is implemented as follows.

An extension of the global Reinhard Operator [16] is used locally. It is called Local Reinhard Operator (LRO) where its used a 3x3 window to obtain the local luminance $R(i)$ as defined by L HDR map, that is, in other words, is $O(x, y)$:

Fig. 1. Block Diagram Pipeline for the FMER implementation.

$$R(i) = \frac{1}{9} \sum_{i=0}^9 m(i) \quad (25)$$

$m(i)$ responds to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m''(i) &= L(i) \left(1 + \frac{L(i)}{4+4L(i)} \right) \\
 m'(i) &= \prod \frac{m''(i)}{L(i)} \\
 m(i) &= m''(i)^{1/2.2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

To extracting details we can use the central pixel from the mapping $m(i)$, here ∇ is the details control parameter:

$$R' = m(4) + \nabla * (m(4) - R) \tag{27}$$

Calculating the contrast can be achieved using the following equation, here α is the control parameter, we re-use the same definition of equation 19 for w_{RGB} , but here considering the current mapping pixel, the exponential part f it is also calculated on this step:

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{RGB} &= w_{RGB(1,1)}(1)^{\frac{f}{\alpha}} \\
 f &= \frac{m(4)}{w_{RGB(1,1)}(1)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

Finally, the new pixel is calculated considering the details, contrast, saturation and luminance. ξ is the saturation control parameter.

$$O'(x, y)_{RGB} = \xi \frac{c_{RGB} R'}{m(4)} \tag{29}$$

5 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

It was used as a general CMOS image sensor coupled it with an inspection Microscope. Several samples that are considered typical and highly reflective are used. A set of images are captured in Auto Exposure (Fig. 2), also a set of multiple-exposures are triggered with a control program sequentially and merged with the reference algorithms and the proposed method. The auto-exposure image will be used as the reference to evaluate the missing details on saturated areas. The four methods previously discussed are rendered and evaluated using the metrics mentioned previously. A set of 25 samples were used, due to space limitation, we present four typical cases that are commonly used with microscopy inspection. These set of images used in the experiments can be seen in figure 2 where are shown the different samples under evaluation.

5.1 Real Time Implementation

Creating HDR content on CPU can be a time-consuming task, especially if the spatial resolution of the frame is greater than SD (720x480). Our algorithm has been efficiently implemented on GPU. Our results have shown that for HD, Full-HD and 4K video frames real-time rendering is achieved.

Fig. 2. Samples used on the experiment and captured with Auto-Exposure mode from the image sensor.

Acquiring the multi-exposure in real-time requires a fast image sensor. The Multiple-exposure technique is implemented using a recursive pipeline to set the exposure times. This process is mainly an independent thread in the CPU. The EV control unit will set the current exposure value to camera's frame. The time is estimated using the following formula:

$$t_w = \begin{cases} \sqrt{|t_{f1} - t_{f2}|} > 350 \\ 350 \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Our experiments have shown that a minimum t_w of $350ms$ are required for a stable exposure burst. As was mentioned, this time gap it is dependent on image sensors' speed. For instance, faster image sensors will generate greater frame rates. Once that the bracketing is active, the frames are sent to the GPU. The processing pipeline is based in shaders, mainly because of its portability and efficiency for image processing tasks. A group of shaders are used where the main algorithms are implemented. A block diagram of the pipeline is shown in figure 1. As depicted in the previous figure, the current frames are copied to the local GPU memory, the merging and tone mapping are apply in GPU's memory. Once the process is finished the rendering is sent back for displaying. After that, the process repeats every two frames.

6 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

6.1 Render Quality

Once that all images are processed, it will be found what algorithms produce the best render output. Two parameters are considered, the SNR and the sharpness (SH) of the renderings. Objective speaking, these parameters will give us enough information about the quality of the proposed merging compared with similar approaches. On the first experiment, it is used an electronic board shown in figure 3. As we can see according to table 1 in the "Board" section, the best performance was for the classic Debebec's method (top right corner image). Although small loss on details on high reflective areas (pinouts of the chip) was observed. Also, this method obtained the highest SNR. Visually our result (bottom right corner image) it is better. However, FMER obtained a medium SNR value.

Fig. 3. Rendering results for the Board: Top left, Average. Top right, Debebec+Reinhard. Bottom left, Mertens. Bottom Right, FMER.

On the second sample depicted in figure 4, it was found that the best render output was for the FMER (bottom right corner image). Also, the highest SNR achieved by our algorithm, the second best render was for the classic Debebec's method (top right corner image). Although, it was possible to see some small artefacts in the highly reflective areas of the sample (black pixels), something that it was addressed on Yujie's paper [17]. Table 1 in the "Metal" section shown the results for each individual case.

Fig. 4. Set of images for the second experiment. Rendering results: Top left, Average. Top right, Devebec+Reinhard. Bottom left, Mertens. Bottom Right, FMER.

Fig. 5. Set of images considered highly reflective. Rendering results: Top left, Average. Top right, Devebec+Reinhard. Bottom left, Mertens. Bottom Right, FMER.

Fig. 6. Set of images considered highly reflective. Rendering results: Top left, Average. Top right, Devebec+Reinhard. Bottom left, Mertens. Bottom Right, FMER.

The third experiment can be considered a very challenging one. It involves highly reflective materials such as chrome, that is considered a specular material. This sample is shown in figure 5. Considering the results of table 1 in the "Bolts" section, the FMER obtained the best response (bottom right corner image). The second best rendering was for Mertens (bottom left corner image). Although, visually speaking, it is possible to see a loss of information over metals' surface with Mertens' method. In contrast, the FMER shows most of the roughness of metals' surface.

Method	Board		Metal		Bolts		Aluminium	
	SNR	SH	SNR	SH	SNR	SH	SNR	SH
Average	-0.330	2900	15.971	4705	14.857	1843	20.302	2025
Dev.+Rein.	14.205	2519	13.063	5172	14.066	2721	17.456	1960
Mertens	13.956	2794	12.760	4493	19.979	2906	22.909	2237
FMER	9.8577	2031	23.625	1843	20.144	1454	23.834	1058

Table 1. Data obtained from the metrics used to evaluate the render quality of the algorithms.

The last sample considers a pressed aluminium sheet, where different patterns such as flat, vertical lines and roughness are present on surface's material at the same time. The sample is shown in figure 6. Considering the results of table 1 in the "Aluminium" section, one more time FMER (bottom right corner image) obtained a high SNR followed by Mertens' method (top right corner image). As we can observe on the specular areas of the image, the FMER obtained more information than

Mertens' method. Finally, it is necessary to mention that overall medium value for SH greater than 1500 can be considered a good response to sharpness details, but this metric also depends on the contrast of the image that has not been considered.

Fig. 7. Results obtained using HDR-VQM for the four experiments with different samples. Bottom row shows the best rendering according to this metric. (Left-Right: Devebec, FMER, Devebec, Mertens)

The last experiment involves the analysis of the HDR-VQM metric. It was found that in 50% of the samples was better the classic Devebec's method. A tie between Mertens and FMER method was a curious case showing that our algorithm is very competitive. The results can be seen in figure 7, as matter of fact it was observed that all evaluated methods had a different response, this leads us to think in the following questions: some content affect the metrics? Is it not possible to use a single method for different samples? These questions need further research that we are working on it.

6.2 Image Improvement

It is made the assumption that a reference image can help us to understand how much improvement has been done. For doing so, it is imperative to have these set of references images. In this manner we are able to compare the results, it is considered a first picture as the normal image captured by sensors' automatic configuration, and a second picture that can be used to compare the merging algorithms. The most simple way for this second picture is based on the following assumption, it is created a reference image based on the average blending. In this manner, we can make a reference that is overall neutral to any specific algorithm. In this experiment, it is evaluated two possible cases. The first one is the auto-exposure system (AE) of the camera and the second the average blending (AVE). Table 2 shows the results after applying the Minkowski metric. It is possible to say that 75% of the times, the FMER method gives the best results against conventional auto-exposure systems.

Fig. 8. Results obtained using ROIs for the four experiments with different samples to evaluate what method recovers more information in the high luminance areas. Bottom row shows the best renderings according to the selected ROI.(Left-Right: FMER, Debevec, FMER, FMER)

Using the second image (average blending) as the reference image and according to our experiments (Table 2), it was found that there is a 50% of improvement against the auto-exposure system. Curiously, FMER had 25% of improvement against the

AE→HDR Methods				
Sample	AVE	DEB	MERT	FMER
Board	30.441	26.545	30.529	22.303
Steal	16.823	6.560	11.385	29.726
Bolts	30.849	37.055	24.774	45.472
Alum	20.338	38.327	29.713	47.165
AVE→HDR Methods				
Board	30.441	49.429	54.326	25.908
Steal	16.883	15.473	25.465	29.648
Bolts	30.849	8.8617	38.787	24.168
Alum	20.338	21.844	29.186	29.530

Table 2. **Improvement comparing the Auto-Exposure (AE) / Average (AVE) system against different HDR methods.**

average blending. And Mertens’ method was 50% better against the average blending. It is necessary to say, that the visual appearance and recovery of details were not considered in this experiment.

6.3 Details Recovering

A region of interest (ROI) were analysed for all the experiments. This ROI was selected where the details recovering are observed on the high luminance areas. It was compared the same region over different rendering methods and the reference images (Auto-exposure and average blending). The only measure that can give us a good modelling of the details recovering is the Kurtosis. After doing many experiments it was found that the smaller kurtosis among the group will indicate that the current area under study contains more details or recovered information. The results can be seen graphically in figure 8. The FMER obtained up to 75% of recovered details, followed by Debevec and Mertens’ methods. As we can see in figure 8 there is a significant difference when is compared with the details recovered by FMER with the reference images. Similarly, the same effect can be seen with the other methods.

7 REMARKS

In this publication common methods for obtaining a well-exposed image/video were briefly reviewed, then an alternative method to generate high-quality HDR video in real-time is proposed and compared using general objective metrics for its correct interpretation. It was measured and analysed its performance with standard HDR algorithms. A series of tests have been carried out with typical samples, showing good renderings of the captured frames. The proposed method called FMER clearly shows an overall improvement of 75% when is compared with similar approaches. Our results are highly competitive with those shown in the literature. Furthermore,

its ability to be implemented in real-time for GPU or hardware devices makes this algorithm suitable for production. Currently, this method is implemented in HDR Microscopy systems that are used for inspection systems based on Bright Field and Dark Field applications.

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García Bernal SALVADOR Received his BEng in Electronics and Computers from UDLA-P and M.Sc. in Electronics from ITOV, México (2003, 2006 respectively). He received a PhD in Computer Sciences from the University of Nottingham, UK. (2015). His main research areas are in HDR imaging and video, image processing, image indexing, hardware design, among others. Currently, he is a researcher and Software Engineer at Novel Optics, China.

Zheng CHI Received his BS and M. Sc. in Information and Communication Engineering from Zhejiang University (2009, 2013 respectively). He was awarded a PhD in 2017 by the University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China, in Computer Sciences. Currently, he is a researcher and Software Engineer at Novel Optics, China. His research interests are in HDR imaging and video technologies, 3D microscopy, and image processing.

Zhang KEQI got his BSc. from the Department of Optical Instruments, Zhejiang University in 1982, and a PhD from Chinese Academy of Science, Shanghai Institute of Technical Physics in 1989. Zhang was awarded as a distinguished expert of "the National Thousands of People Plan". Currently, he is the deputy director of science and technology of Ningbo Yongxin Optics Co., Ltd.

Evaluating A HDR Algorithm for Real-Time Microscopic Inspection Systems.

Mao LEI got his BSc from the Department of Optical Instruments, Zhejiang University in 1982, Master of EMBA at 2008. He has worked as professor and Engineer. Currently, enjoy special government allowances of the State Council. Currently, he is the general manager of Ningbo Yongxin Optics Co., Ltd.

kuang CUIFANG Received his PhD at Beijing Jiaotong University in 2007. Kuang was a Postdoctoral researcher at the University of South Carolina and He has been visiting researcher at Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Currently, he is Associate Professor at Zhejiang University, China. His research interests are in Super Resolution Microscopy technologies, Optical Imaging and Modern Optical Microscope Instruments.

Liu Xu Obtained his BS. and MS. from Zhejiang University in 1984 and 1986 respectively. Received his PhD from Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Physique de Marseille in France in 1990. Currently, he is Changjiang Chair at Zhejiang University, China. His research interests are in Super Resolution Microscopy technologies, Computation Imaging and Biophotonics.